

Electrochemical investigation of anticorrosive properties of nano-crystalline $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ green ceramic pigments synthesized by microwave-assisted gel combustion method

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Abstract : In present work, $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ green ceramic pigments were synthesized by microwave-assisted gel combustion method. Two different fuels; citric acid and glycine were used. Products were characterized by X-ray diffraction, Fourier transform of infrared, Scanning-Transition Electron Microscopy and diffuse reflectance. The anticorrosive properties of the obtained pigments were investigated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy techniques. Results have shown that by citric acid a calcination step was needed to obtain the desired phase whereas by glycine pure ZnO phase was obtained directly. Transition Electron Microscopy demonstrated the quasi-spherical and rod-like particles with mean particle size of 70 and 150 nm for glycine and citric acid respectively. The corrosion performances of the coating in 3% w/v NaCl solution were evaluated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and polarization measurements. According to the measurements of EIS and electrochemical polarization, the coatings with glycine-based pigment showed a highest corrosion resistance among the prepared coatings. It was revealed from polarization tests that higher corrosion potential and lower corrosion current was obtained for coatings with glycine-based pigment.

Keywords : Combustion, microwave-assisted, pigment, anticorrosive, mild steel electrode.

Introduction

Corrosion of iron and mild steel is a fundamental academic and industrial concern that has received a considerable amount of attention¹. The use of inhibitors is one of the most practical methods for protection against corrosion, especially in acidic media². The progress in this field has been phenomenal in recent years and is borne out by the output of literature³. Acid and NaCl solutions are widely used in industry, the most important fields of application being acid pickling, industrial acid cleaning and oil well acidizing. Because of the general aggressiveness of acid solutions, inhibitors are commonly used to reduce the corrosive attack on metallic materials. Most of the well known inhibitors are organic compounds containing nitrogen, sulfur and oxygen atoms. The influence

of organic compounds containing nitrogen, such as amines and heterocyclic compounds, on the corrosion of steel in acidic and NaCl solutions has been investigated by several works⁴⁻⁷. Many of corrosion inhibitors were based on ceramic pigments which have good adsorption on steel surface. The anticorrosive properties of the ceramic pigments based on ZnO doped with cobalt have been investigated⁸ and they have shown the combination of cobalt and zinc oxides improve the anticorrosive properties of the obtained pigments. Furthermore, the green colored oxides of ZnCo-O system, with low Co content, have been interested as new environmental friendly colored pigments and they can be used as substitution of chromium oxides. Solution combustion synthesis method is one of the most interesting synthesis routes for produc-

tion of homogenous nano-crystalline single and multi-component oxides. The great advantage of this technique for preparing ceramic materials resides in the ability to achieve high purity single and multiphase complex oxide powders. Generally, solution combustion process is based on exothermic reaction of metal nitrates with fuel in low temperatures. Numerous studies have been used to prepare, zirconia pigment⁹, cobalt pigments¹⁰, Y_2BaCuO_5 pigment¹¹, spinel based pigment¹² by synthesis method. Recently a novel technique called 'microwave-assisted combustion synthesis' is used to synthesize oxide materials¹³. Microwave heating can be more advantageous than conventional heating because of short processing time and volumetric heating¹⁴. The application of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy technique (EIS) as a new tool in corrosion research has resulted in a wealth of information concerning the methods of corrosion protection which were difficult to study with traditional dc techniques. This includes corrosion protection by conversion coatings¹⁵, polymer coating, and anodic films¹⁶. EIS has also provided information concerning corrosion protection by inhibitors¹⁷. In addition to specification of the physical properties of the system, the technique has led to important mechanistic and kinetic information¹⁸. Potentiodynamic polarization and EIS techniques are applied to study the ability of ceramic pigment as a non-ionic surfactant (NS) to inhibit the corrosion of mild steel in 3% w/v NaCl solution. Kalendová have investigated effects of particle sizes and shapes of zinc metal on the properties of anticorrosive coatings¹⁹. It was demonstrated that better results in term of anticorrosion efficiency were found by using small zinc particles in the coating. The effect of the nano ZnO particles addition on the corrosion, mechanical and optical properties of alkyd-based waterborne coating was investigated by Dhoke *et al.*²⁰.

In present work, $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ green ceramic pigments were synthesized by the microwave-assisted gel combustion method. Two different fuels being citric acid and glycine were used. The anticorrosive properties of the obtained pigments have been investigated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy technique.

Experimental

(i) Preparation of pigments :

All the raw materials in this research were of analytical

grade. $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck), $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Merck) as an oxidant and citric and glycine as fuel and complexing agent were used. According to propellant chemistry²¹, combustion of $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ by citric acid can be written by following equation :

The exothermic redox reaction between zinc nitrate, cobalt nitrate and glycine can be expressed as follows :

Metal nitrates and fuels were dissolved in distilled water to form a solution in which Zn^{2+} and Co^{2+} concentration meet the formula of $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$.

After adding metal nitrates and fuel (citric acid or glycine) to deionized water in beaker vessel, the obtained solution was heated on hotplate (80–90 °C) until the excess water was removed and a highly viscous precursor gel was gained. The beaker vessel was transferred into microwave oven (Samsung, Korea, 900 W, 2.45 GHz frequency) to complete the combustion reaction. All experiments were performed in maximum power of microwave for 50 s. The powders were calcined in a chamber furnace at different temperatures varying from 800 to 1100 °C.

(ii) Corrosion tests :

As-prepared pigments were incorporated in an alkyd-based coating system in 2% wt%. The dispersion was done using a mechanical stirrer followed by ultrasonication. The nano-composite coating was applied on pretreated steel test panels (76.2 mm × 152.4 mm × 0.8 mm) by an appropriate applicator. A steel sheet was used as working electrode. The exposed surface area of each electrode was 1 cm². Prior to the coating of the surface, the surface pretreatment of the working electrode was performed by mechanical polishing of the electrode surface with successive grades of emery papers down to 1200 grit up to a mirror finish. The electrode was then, rinsed with acetone and distilled water before film formation of the experiments were performed in a 100 cm³ volume cell at 20 °C, using a platinum and calomel as auxiliary and reference electrodes, respectively. The

experiments were carried out in 3% w/v NaCl solution. All solutions were freshly prepared from analytical grade chemical reagents (Merck) using doubly distilled water and were used without further purification. For each run, a freshly prepared solution as well as a new sample of electrodes was used.

(iii) *Characterization techniques :*

A D-500 (Siemens, Karlsruhe, Germany) Diffractometer was used for XRD analysis. Morphology analysis was performed using LEO 1455VP (Oxford, UK) Scanning Electron Microscope. The IR spectra of the dried gel and calcined powder were given by FT-IR (Spectrum one, FT-IR spectrometer, Perkin-Elmer). Ultraviolet radiation spectroscopy in the visible-ultraviolet light region was conducted with a 7000 A spectrometer (Gretag Macbeth) in the range between 350 and 750 nm for determination of diffuse reflectance of the obtained pigments. $L^*a^*b^*$ color parameters of the heat-treated powders were measured using the standard lighting D65, according to the CIE- $L^*a^*b^*$ colorimetric method recommended by the CIE. Electrochemical studies were carried out in a conventional three electrode cell powered by an electrochemical system comprising of EG&G model 273 potentiostat/galvanostat and Solartron model 1255 fre-

quency response analyzer. The system is run by a PC through M270 and M398 commercial software via a GPIB interface.

Results and discussion

(i) *Pigments synthesis :*

Two fuels, citric acid and glycine, were used for combustion synthesis of $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ pigments and the obtained powders were characterized by X-Ray diffractometer. Fig. 1 shows comparison of the obtained patterns. From Fig. 1a when acid citric was used as fuel no phase can be distinguished and the product is generally amorphous. Moderate heat generated by citrate-nitrate reaction may be one of the reasons for such observation. Fig. 2b shows peaks at 31.7, 34.4, 36.2, 47.5, 56.6, 62.9 and 67.9 (2-theta degree) from which are consistent with the JCPDS data of ZnO. No peaks attributable to other phases are observed, indicating the single phase of the zinc oxide. Huge amount of heat generated by glycine-nitrate reaction may be the important reason for such observation. In nitrate-glycine combustion reaction the nitrate ions make an oxidizing medium around metallic ions, which is useful for burning off the organic part of a gel. Glycine is polar and very water-soluble. This increases the rate of the ionization of the glycine to create $^+NH_3$

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ prepared by (a) citric acid and (b) glycine.

CH_2COO^- specie which can cause an increase in combustion reaction rate. From Fig. 1a it seems that in the case of citric acid a calcination step was needed to obtain the pure ZnO phase. Fig. 2 shows the XRD results of combustion synthesized powders as a function of calcina-

calculated powder, a broad intense band at $450\text{--}540\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be observed. Broad band around 440 cm^{-1} is due to asymmetric stretching mode of the tetrahedral ZnO_4 group present in the wurtzite ZnO structure²². Fig. 4 shows SEM images of $\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}$ prepared by using (a)-citric

Fig. 2. XRD pattern of $\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}$ prepared by citric acid as a function of calcination temperature.

tion temperature. According to Fig. 2, it is obvious that with increase of calcination temperature, decomposition of Co_3O_4 occurred and cobalt entered to ZnO crystal structure. Main Co_3O_4 peaks at 37° disappear at 900°C and ZnO peaks are broad which is due to complete entrance of cobalt in ZnO structure. The crystallite size of the samples has been calculated by Scherrer formula on the XRD patterns. They were in the range of 30 nm and 37 nm for glycine and citric acid respectively.

Chemical and structural changes that take place during combustion can be monitored by a spectroscopic analysis. Fig. 3 shows the IR spectra of the dried gel and powder calcinated at 900°C in the range of $450\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for stoichiometric ratio of citric acid. The dried gel showed the characteristic bands around 3400 , 1600 and 1380 cm^{-1} corresponding to the O-H group, carboxyl group and NO_3^- ion, respectively. In the IR curves of the

acid after calcination and (b) glycine. From Fig. 4a it seems that particles were partially sintered and grain growth was occurred during calcination. Fig. 4b shows the as-prepared $\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}$ sample is spongy and porous agglomerates with pore size about $0.1\text{--}5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. During the combustion process, gases were given out instantly, leading to the formation of the pores. Fig. 5 shows TEM images of $\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}$ solid solution prepared by (a) citric acid and (b) glycine as fuel. From Fig. 5a, the rod like particles are observed with mean particle size of 150 nm. Fig. 5b shows quasi-spherical particles with mean particle size of 70 nm. It seems that in the case of citric acid the calcination step has caused the growth in the particle size. This can be related to huge tendency of sinterability of the particles by combustion synthesis²³. This tendency is due to an increase in surface area and surface energy, which are driving force for sintering.

In order to study the color properties of $\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}$

Fig. 3. FT-IR spectra of dried gel and calcined powder at 900 °C for citric acid as fuel

Fig. 4. SEM images of $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ powder prepared by (a) citric acid and calcined at 900 °C (b) glycine

Fig. 5. The photos by TEM of the samples (a) citric acid and calcined at 900 °C (b) glycine

pigments, effect of fuel type on color properties have been investigated Table 1 shows the result of the colo-

Sample	L^*	a^*	b^*	C^*
Citric acid	42.3	-11.1	4.5	14.00
Glycine	43.6	-17.3	6.1	18.34

rimetric coordinates (L^* , a^* , b^* , C^*) for citric acid and glycine samples. The pigment derived by glycine indicates more green color due to larger value of a^* compared to citric acid. This confirms that different color properties are obtained which can be well related to powder particle and state of agglomeration. From data of C^* it is concluded that glycine-based sample has more chromaticity and has a dipper green color.

(ii) Electrochemical investigation :

In order to study, the influence of the inhibitors on the corrosion resistance of steel panels, we performed a potentiodynamic study on steel in NaCl solutions for pigment prepared by glycine and citric acid and the results were compared to bare electrode without any pigment. Fig. 6 shows typical potentiodynamic polarization curves recorded for steel electrode in solution containing 3% w/v NaCl for different prepared samples with and without

Fig. 6. Typical potentiodynamic anodic and cathodic polarization curves recorded for steel in 3% w/v NaCl solution in the absence and presence of the inhibitor on surface of electrode.

pigments : W; the pigment from glycine, C; the pigment from citric acid and A; film without any pigment. The polarization curves show Tafel type behavior of these samples. Tafel calculations are listed in Table 2, where E_{corr} , I_{corr} , CR, β_a , β_c and IE ($IE = (I_{blank} - I_{inhi})/I_{blank}$)²⁴ are the corrosion potential, corrosion current density, corrosion rate, anode Tafel constant, cathode Tafel constant and inhibition efficiency, respectively. The open circuit corrosion potentials, E_{corr} , are drifted to more positive values and a significant decrease of the corrosion current was observed on the steel substrate in presence of

C and W. These results indicate that these inhibitors act generally as anodic inhibitor. According to the data of Table 2, it is obvious that in the presence of the inhibitor, the corrosion rate of the samples decreases in the order : A > C > W. It seems that quasi-spherical particles with mean particle size of 70 nm have better corrosion inhibi-

Table 2. Polarization parameters in the corrosion of steel electrode in 3% w/v NaCl solution in the absence and presence of inhibitors at 25 °C

Sample	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} (mA cm ⁻²)	Tafel slope β_a (mV dec ⁻¹)	Tafel slope β_c (mV dec ⁻¹)	IE%
A	-657	15.8	181	640	-
C	-525	1.05	412	523	0.93
W	-375	0.5	287	275	0.96

tion surface than the rod-like ones with mean particle size of 150 nm. This can be due to the better adhesion and compression of quasi-spherical particles with mean particle size of 70 nm.

On the other hand this phenomenon can be explained easily by filling free spaces between particles of smaller sizes. At larger particles the filling of pores by means of oxide is incomplete and the leakages can lead to more easy liquid and gas penetrations through the paint film. With particles of rode-like type the sealing of rather voluminous pores at coating is difficult, and the coatings exhibit a lower anticorrosion efficiency. Fig. 7 shows typical potentiodynamic polarization curves recorded for steel electrode in solution containing 3% w/v NaCl in the absence and presence of C and W after seven days im-

Fig. 7. Typical potentiodynamic anodic and cathodic polarization curves recorded for steel after 7 days immersion of electrode in 3% w/v NaCl solution in the absence and presence of the inhibitor on surface of electrode.

mersion of steel sample in solution containing 3% w/v NaCl. As can be after seven days the protective effect of inhibitor layer of C and W was not obviously changed. Tafel calculations after seven days immersion are listed in Table 3. In order to get more information about the corrosion inhibition phenomenon, solution resistance (R_s), charge-transfer resistance (R_p), double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) of steel electrode, impedance measurements have

Table 3. Polarization parameters in the corrosion of steel electrode after 7 days immersion in 3% w/v NaCl solution in the absence and presence of inhibitors at 25 °C

Sample	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} (mA cm ⁻²)	Tafel slope β_a (mV dec ⁻¹)	Tafel slope β_c (mV dec ⁻¹)	IE%
A	-625	19.9	101	629	-
C	-589	7.9	350	401	0.6
W	-575	1.25	125	205	0.93

been carried out in chloride solutions in the absence and presence of the inhibitors at the OCP. The Nyquist plot for steel sample in 0.2 M NaCl solution at OCP and at 25 °C is shown in Fig. 8a. The data reveal that impedance diagram consists of a capacitive loop due to charge transfer resistance and double layer capacitance. Bode phase plots for the same sample is shown in Fig. 8b. Distinguishable peak are observed in the Bode plots corresponding to semicircles in the Nyquist plot. The equivalent circuit compatible with the Nyquist diagram recorded in the presence of alcohols was depicted in Fig. 9. To obtain a satisfactory impedance simulation of corrosion, it is necessary to replace the capacitor C with a constant phase element (CPE), Q , in the equivalent circuit. In this electrical equivalent circuit, R_s , CPE_{dl} and R_{ct} represent solution resistance, a constant phase element corresponding to the double layer capacitance and the charge transfer resistance.

To corroborate the equivalent circuit, the experimental data are fitted to equivalent circuit and the circuit elements are obtained. Table 4 illustrates the equivalent circuit parameters for the impedance spectra of corrosion of steel in NaCl solution. As can be seen from Table 2, presence of inhibitors, increase the diameters of semi-circle in Nyquist diagrams.

Fig. 8. (a) The Nyquist plots for steel sample in 3% w/v NaCl solution at OCP and at 25 °C in absence (a) and presence of inhibitors. (b) The Bode plots for steel sample in same solution and inhibitors.

Fig. 9. The equivalent circuit model used to analyze the experimental data presented in Fig. 7.

Table 4. Equivalent circuit parameters in the corrosion of steel electrode in 3% w/v NaCl solution in the absence and presence of inhibitors at 25 °C

Sample	R_s (Ω)	$C_d \times 10^5$ (F)	R_{ct} (Ω)	n
A	42	6.1	5152	0.85
C	44	2.2	17223	0.8
W	45	0.91	41325	0.83

Conclusion :

In this investigation, $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ green ceramic pigments were successfully synthesized by microwave-as-

sisted gel combustion method. X-Ray results have shown a calcination step was needed to obtain the desired phase when citric acid was used as fuel whereas by glycine pure ZnO phase was obtained directly. Transition Electron Microscopy demonstrated the quasi-spherical and rode-like particles with mean particle size of 70 and 150 nm for glycine and citric acid respectively. Color properties investigation of $Zn_{0.9}Co_{0.1}O$ pigments have shown the pigment derived by glycine indicated more green color. Investigations of the corrosion inhibition of steel electrode in solution containing chloride ions through electrochemical methods demonstrated that the coatings with glycine-based pigment showed better corrosion resistance and lower corrosion current. It was revealed that these coatings were more compact and uniform rather than the coatings with citric acid-based pigment.

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